

Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Adversarial Defense in Vehicular Communication Systems

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Abstract—One of the key concerns related to the pervasive integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) models in vehicular-to-everything (V2X) communication systems pertains to adversarial attacks, which may lead trained models to exhibit undesirable behaviors. As security and user safety are tightly coupled in V2X, ensuring the resilience of AI/ML models against adversaries becomes indispensable. However, addressing adversarial attacks poses a challenging task, requiring appropriate countermeasures to elevate the trustworthiness of the targeted AI/ML models. In this paper, we propose a deep reinforcement learning (DRL)-based approach to defend against two data poisoning attacks, namely label-flipping and policy induction. Extensive evaluation with the aid of an open-source dataset demonstrates that our scheme outperforms benchmark classifiers, achieving significantly superior detection performance in the presence of label-flipping attacks. The effectiveness of our DRL-based approach is also showcased under different adversarial strategies in the policy induction attack.

Index Terms—DRL, Adversarial ML, Poisoning attacks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transformative potential of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) models drive a paradigm shift in vehicle-to-everything (V2X) connectivity and provide a fertile ground for novel data-driven services. Nevertheless, incorporating AI/ML techniques in vehicular communication systems is a double-edged sword. The advanced capabilities fueled by computational methods and tools come inadvertently with security risks and compelling attack surfaces that can be exploited for malicious purposes [1]. In particular, the inherent vulnerabilities and lack of robustness of AI/ML models may give rise to finely targeted, stealthy, and scalable attacks which ultimately lead to V2X user safety concerns, traffic disruption, and privacy violations [2].

Attacks on AI/ML models can be categorized as causative or exploratory, depending on whether they aim to disrupt the training or inference phase of the targeted model, respectively. In data poisoning, a special case of causative attack, an adversary deliberately tampers the training samples, by injecting carefully crafted malicious inputs or by polluting the original data to influence the learning outcome [3]. Such poisoning attacks may be efficient against automated feature selection methods [4] used in classification tasks for vehicular attack prevention and intrusion detection [5]. The authors in [6] demonstrate experimentally the capabilities of AI/ML-guided adversaries to deceive existing ML classifiers for vehicular

misbehavior detection. Additional security threats may arise when adversaries aim at disclosing information about the applied model. Model inversion attacks, for example, focus on retrieving the training data by utilizing the outputs of the targeted model, e.g., using gradient inversion [7]. Besides adversarial attacks, an inappropriate format of input training data, owing to vehicular sensor malfunctions or reading errors, may further exacerbate the resilience of AI/ML models [8].

Dealing with such challenges often becomes non-trivial, calling for adversarial defense mechanisms to elevate the trustworthiness of AI-based vehicular communication systems [9]. Blockchain has been recently adopted to achieve privacy preservation and trust management in V2X [10], [11]. While its distributed nature and immutability features can foster trust in decentralized learning setups [12], the reliance on network consensus and the vulnerabilities of smart contracts represent key open issues. On the other hand, employing homomorphic encryption ensures privacy via model training on encrypted vehicular data, at the expense of increased computational complexity for key establishment [13]. While approaches like adversarial training and defense distillation can enhance robustness, AI/ML models may still be susceptible to adversarial samples generated through transferability-based black-box attacks [3], [14]. In this context, the authors in [15] introduce an adversarial deep reinforcement learning (DRL) algorithm to enhance the robustness of autonomous vehicle dynamics by mitigating the impact of false data injection attacks. An interpretable method proposed in [16] aims to identify location forging attacks with the aid of a boosting decision tree ensemble to enhance confidence in the accuracy of predicted decisions.

In this work, we introduce a novel DRL-based approach to provide adversarial defense in vehicular communication systems involving geographically distributed roadside units (RSUs). Our study considers two data poisoning attacks, namely label-flipping and policy induction attacks, launched against RSUs that perform vehicular data classification tasks. The goal of the adversaries is to influence the learning outcomes by causing misclassification of the training samples. An in-depth performance assessment using an open-source dataset demonstrates the robustness of our scheme in the presence of different adversarial strategies. In addition, when compared against benchmark classifiers, our DRL-based defense mechanism is shown to be superior in detecting label-flipping attacks.

Fig. 1: Vehicular network scenario.

II. NETWORK SCENARIO AND ATTACK MODEL

In this section, we describe the network scenario under study and the considered attack models.

A. Scenario

Fig. 1 illustrates the network scenario under consideration, where vehicles periodically transmit basic safety messages (BSMs) containing real-time mobility information. These messages are received by RSUs from vehicles within their coverage. BSMs encompass the position, speed, acceleration, and heading angle of each vehicle, and other relevant data. In our setup, vehicles and RSUs are authenticated and authorized by the central/local authority. In contrast to our prior work in [17], RSUs are considered to be susceptible to adversarial attacks. Each RSU is equipped with a DRL-based detection system with the capability of detecting misbehaviors, including poisoning attacks and abnormal perturbations resulting from adversaries, sensor malfunctions, or reading errors. The DRL model is trained on the RSU due to its superior computational resources compared to in-vehicle resources. Upon receiving streaming vehicular data as BSMs, the RSU engages in real-time downstream classification.

B. Adversarial Attack Models

We assume the presence of adversaries attempting to contaminate the training data and realize data poisoning attacks on DRL models. In this context, we consider two poisoning attacks associated with adversarial ML: *i*) label-flipping and *ii*) policy induction attacks. In both cases, the goal is to maliciously influence the learning model by forcing incorrect outcomes in downstream classification tasks.

1) *Label-flipping*: In this attack, adversaries are assumed to be rogue insiders who contribute to the training data or have access to the training data itself. We consider an attacker who targets the malicious class to flip the labels

Fig. 2: Policy induction attack on DRL model.

of certain training data instances at an RSU. In this scenario, the adversary randomly selects a set of malicious samples and flips the labels of their data instances into genuine ones, resulting in a targeted random label-flipping attack (Definition 1). The purpose is to compromise the model's detection performance and force the downstream task to misclassify or generalize incorrectly on the test data. In Definition 1, $D_{\mathcal{R}_i}$ denotes the training data of the RSU \mathcal{R}_i , i.e., $D_{\mathcal{R}_i} = \{(x_{\mathcal{R}_{i1}}, y_{\mathcal{R}_{i1}}), \dots, (x_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}}, y_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}}), \dots, (x_{\mathcal{R}_{iN}}, y_{\mathcal{R}_{iN}})\}$, with $x_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}} \in X_{\mathcal{R}_i}$ as the k -th instance of $D_{\mathcal{R}_i}$ while $y_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}} \in Y_{\mathcal{R}_i}$ represents the corresponding label of $x_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}}$.

Definition 1 (Label-flipping attack). Given training samples $\{x_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}}, y_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}}\}_{k=1}^N$ of $D_{\mathcal{R}_i}$, belonging to an RSU \mathcal{R}_i with $x_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}} \in X_{\mathcal{R}_i}$ and $y_{\mathcal{R}_{ik}} \in Y_{\mathcal{R}_i} = \{0, 1\}$, a poisoning attack is defined as a targeted random label-flipping attack when the attacker randomly selects a fraction $\zeta \in (0, 1]$ of malicious samples and flips the label of the corresponding training samples from 1 (i.e., malicious) to 0 (i.e., genuine).

2) *Policy Induction*: Considering the vulnerability of DRL models to adversarial perturbations in state observations, we focus on policy induction attacks on DRL in the context of adversarial ML [18]. The objective of the policy induction attack is to intentionally influence the DRL policy, leading to inaccurate outcomes in downstream classification. To implement policy induction, we appropriately adapt the adversarial attack initially presented in [19] within the context of DRL.

Assume an external attacker acting as a man-in-the-middle between the target and the environment, as illustrated in Fig. 2, with the capability to alter the state observation before it is explored by the target. The attacker employs a black-box technique and exploits the transferability of adversarial examples, as outlined in [14]. The Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) algorithm is utilized [20] to generate adversarial examples. The FGSM crafts a new adversarial input that maximizes the loss $L(\theta, x, y)$. Given input x , the adversarial input x' generated by the FGSM is expressed as

$$x' = x + \epsilon * \text{sign}(\nabla_x L(\theta, x, y)), \quad (1)$$

where y is the label of input x , ϵ denotes a small multiplier, θ are the model parameters, and L represents the loss. The adversarial perturbation is constrained with an upper bound on \mathcal{L}_∞ norm, ensuring that $\|x' - x\|_\infty \leq \epsilon$. The operational procedure of the policy induction attack is elaborated in Definition 2 as follows.

Definition 2 (Policy induction attack). The attacker induces an arbitrary adversarial policy π_{adv} on the target deep Q-network (DQN) by injecting adversarial examples into training data. The policy π_{adv} is obtained by generating reward values that are exact opposites of the target DQN policy. Given state observation s_{t+1} , the attacker crafts a perturbation vector ($\hat{\delta}_{t+1}$) using FGSM and injects it into the target DQN's state space, as

$$a'_{adv} \leftarrow \pi_{adv}(s_{t+1}), \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{\delta}_{t+1} \leftarrow \text{FGSM}(\hat{Q}', a'_{adv}, s_{t+1}), \quad (3)$$

$$s'_{t+1} \leftarrow s_{t+1} + \hat{\delta}_{t+1}. \quad (4)$$

Crafting adversarial inputs s'_t and s'_{t+1} requires minimizing the loss function in (5) to force the target DQN towards incorrect action a' , given state s_t , as

$$\min_{\theta'} (y_t - Q'(s_t, a_t; \theta'))^2, \quad (5)$$

where $y_t = r_t + \gamma \max_{a'} \hat{Q}'(s'_{t+1}, a'; \theta'_-)$ and Q' , \hat{Q}' are the replica DQNs of the target DQN.

III. DRL-BASED ADVERSARIAL DEFENSE

This section presents the DRL-based approach for adversarial attack detection in the considered scenario in Fig. 1.

A. RL for Adversarial Attack Detection

Markov decision process (MDP) offers a modeling framework [21] for the detection of adversarial data with sequential decision-making over vehicular data traces. An MDP is defined as a tuple of five elements, i.e., $\mathcal{M} = \langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{R}, \gamma \rangle$, where \mathcal{S} is the set of states, \mathcal{A} the set of actions, $\mathcal{P} : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \mapsto [0, 1]$ is the state transition probabilities function, $\mathcal{R} : \mathcal{S} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ denotes the reward function with a set of possible rewards, and $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ denotes the discount factor which reflects the importance of immediate and long-term future rewards. The action of detection will change the environment based on the decision of either genuine or malicious behavior at time-step t ; subsequently, the next decision at time-step $t+1$ will be influenced by the changing environment at the previous time-step t .

B. DRL Model

As shown in Fig. 1, the aggregated vehicular data at the RSU form a time-series repository of received BSMs with intrinsic temporal and spatial interdependencies. In this work, we consider a DRL-based detector deployed at the edge RSU. The detector (agent) interacts with the vehicular environment to learn the optimal detection policy π^* . Based on the current state s_t , the agent takes an action a_t to maximize its reward r_t . The agent is then rewarded by the environment, and the environment moves to state s_{t+1} following the MDP. This is iterated until the optimal detection policy π^* is learned.

The Q-learning method is implemented to train the RL model for the estimation of the action-value function $Q(s, a)$ [22]. To efficiently manage large state-action space, we rely on deep learning for function approximation. Specifically,

we employ DQN to approximate the action-value function $Q(s, a)$. As a result, the agent with the DQN can efficiently learn to map input states to Q-values. The ϵ -greedy method is used while training to strike a balance between exploration and exploitation in the agent strategy. We hereby describe the components pertaining to the RL model.

The **agent** receives the vehicular data as a time-series and prior decisions as inputs (i.e., state s_t), and generates the new decision made (i.e., action a_t) as output. At each time-step t , the agent's a_t is selected by the policy π . The agent's experience, i.e., $e_t = \langle s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1} \rangle$, stores all the behaviors of the detector. The detector gradually improves by leveraging experience with experience replay memory [23], aiming for a better estimation of the $Q(s, a)$ function. During this process, the agent randomly samples a minibatch of transitions, i.e., $\{s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}\}$, from the replay memory to update the learning model. The aim is to maximize the expected sum of future discounted rewards by learning the optimal detection policy. The discounted reward return is expressed as

$$R_t = \sum_{k=t}^T \gamma^{k-t} r_k, \quad (6)$$

where T represents the length of a training episode. Q-learning model updates are performed with learning rate α as

$$Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow (1 - \alpha)Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha[r_t + \gamma \max_{a_{t+1}} Q(s_{t+1}, a_{t+1})]. \quad (7)$$

The **environment** oversees the agent's training. Following the execution of a_t , the agent receives a reward r_t and observes the next state s_{t+1} . As shown in Fig. 1, the environment contains a large population of BSMs with ground truth information generated via the procedure described in Section IV-A.

The **state** contains the sequence of previous actions denoted by $s_{action} = \langle a_{t-1}, a_t, \dots, a_{t+n-1} \rangle$, and the current BSM information denoted by $s_{time} = \langle X_t, X_{t+1}, \dots, X_{t+n} \rangle$. $X_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a d -dimensional feature vector at time-step t , including information on d different features. The agent's next action at s_{t+1} depends on its previous actions and the current information in vehicular data, allowing it to effectively capture temporal dependencies and make informed decisions.

The **action** space is defined as $\mathcal{A} = \{0, 1\}$, where 1 indicates the detection of a malicious sample and 0 represents the genuine behavior. The deterministic detection policy π can be expressed as a mapping, i.e., $\pi : \mathcal{S} \mapsto \mathcal{A}$, from states to actions, where $\pi(s_t)$ denotes the action that the agent takes at state s_t . In a given state s_t , the agent selects the action based on the optimal detection policy given by

$$\pi^* = \arg \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} Q^*(s, a). \quad (8)$$

The **reward** r_t stimulates the agent in exploring various states within the environment and finding an effective detection policy. A numerical value for r_t is assigned based on the ground truth information of BSMs. Specifically, a positive reward is given to the agent for correctly detecting a malicious

sample, i.e., true positive (TP), or a normal state, i.e., true negative (TN). A negative reward is otherwise provided for incorrect identification of a genuine sample as a malicious one, i.e., false positive (FP), or a malicious sample as genuine, i.e., false negative (FN). The agent is penalized more for FN actions than for FPs, as the correct identification of malicious data is necessary to avoid hazardous situations.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section outlines the numerical results obtained for label-flipping and policy induction attacks using our DRL-based detection algorithm, and a performance comparison against two benchmark schemes. The attacks were generated by leveraging the VeReMi dataset [8], which is detailed below.

A. Dataset Description and Pre-processing

The VeReMi dataset includes 19 different misbehavior types, with each type having its own dataset. Each dataset comprises a set of log files containing BSM data exchanged with neighboring vehicles throughout their entire trajectory. Within each misbehavior type dataset, there exists a ground truth file that records the observed behavior of all participating vehicles. BSMs are composed of a three-dimensional vector, encapsulating parameters such as position, speed, acceleration, and heading angle. The ratio between malicious and genuine vehicles in VeReMi is 30%:70% for all simulations.

Through feature analysis and data pre-processing, we identified six fields, namely timestamp, pseudo-identity, position, speed, acceleration, and heading angle, from a BSM payload. These fields were deemed the most relevant feature set to effectively identify misbehaviors from genuine behaviors. To reduce dimensionality, we use the Euclidean norm to compute a scalar representation of the position, speed, acceleration, and heading parameters. In VeReMi, labels were generated by comparing ground truth data against transmitted data in the log files. Misbehavior label 1 was assigned if the data diverged from the ground truth; otherwise, label 0 was assigned.

B. Adversarial Examples

For adversarial examples generation, we select a subset of misbehavior types in VeReMi. This selection aims to provide sufficient coverage for label-flipping and policy induction attacks. To generate adversarial perturbations for the policy induction attack, genuine samples (class 0) are separated from the considered misbehavior type dataset and used to produce a corresponding proportion of malicious data as class 1. The related percentage of malicious data is generated by perturbing the state observations of the DRL agent with a probability $p \in [0, 1]$. The policy induction attack is implemented in a non-continuous manner, as in [24], with $p=0.3$ for training-time adversarial perturbations, creating an approximate 30% to 70% ratio between genuine and adversarially perturbed samples. Similarly, test-time adversarial perturbations are generated using the FGSM method with different p values.

In the following, we provide a brief description of the selected misbehavior types that are relevant to our study.

Position falsification: A vehicle transmits falsified position coordinates within its communication area. This may lead to different misbehavior variants: i) *Constant Position*, the attacker transmits fixed position coordinates; ii) *Constant Position Offset*, the attacker transmits the real position coordinates with a fixed offset.

Speed falsification: A vehicle transmits falsified speed values in its BSMs. The *Random Speed* misbehavior involves the transmission of newly generated random speed values, resulting in falsified speed values in the BSM.

Sybil: An attacker may utilize multiple valid pseudonyms of compromised vehicles to generate fake traffic, creating a set of ghost vehicles in a particular geographical region.

Disruptive: A vehicle re-transmits previously sent messages by other vehicles, flooding the network with stale data to disrupt the propagation of genuine information.

Data Replay: The attacker replays previously received valid BSMs from other vehicles, using its own ID during the replay and attempting to exploit the conditions present during the original BSM transmission.

C. Detection Performance and Discussion

To assess the detection performance of our DRL-based approach, we compute the *Accuracy*, *Precision*, *Recall*, and *F-score* metrics, by considering both genuine and malicious classes. Since the F-score provides the harmonic mean between precision and recall, higher F-score values indicate better performance in our evaluation. We comparatively assess the detection performance of our DRL-based approach against two benchmarks, namely multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and long short-term memory (LSTM) classifiers [25], for the chosen misbehavior types under the label-flipping attack. We conducted experiments using grid search to identify the optimal model for each benchmark classifier, following the configurations outlined in [25]. In this context, we employ an MLP model with three hidden layers having 100, 50, and 30 units, respectively. The hidden layers utilize the *tanh* activation function, and the *Adam* optimization algorithm is used. The output layer of the MLP model consists of a single node for binary classification, employing the *sigmoid* activation function. The LSTM model comprises an input layer, an LSTM layer with 64 units, and a dense output layer with *sigmoid* activation for binary classification. The LSTM model is trained using the *Adam* algorithm with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 64.

The impact of label-flipping is evaluated by setting the parameter ζ to 0.05 and 0.1, corresponding to the random flipping of 5% and 10% of the BSM labels during training. Both benchmark schemes were trained on identical data, utilizing the same feature set as our DRL-based approach to yield a fair comparison. To evaluate the robustness under different conditions, we assess the learned DRL policy under policy induction attack by generating test-time adversarial perturbations in both non-continuous and continuous manners with $p=0.2$ and $p=1$, respectively. In the case of $p=1$, the

TABLE I: Detection performance under label-flipping attack

Misbehavior Type	Label-flipping (%)	Approach	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-score
Constant Position	5	DRL	0.9944	0.9813	1.0000	0.9905
		LSTM	0.7380	0.5904	0.3334	0.4261
		MLP	0.7497	0.6828	0.2654	0.3823
	10	DRL	0.9931	0.9795	0.9971	0.9882
		LSTM	0.7363	0.5992	0.2915	0.3922
		MLP	0.7543	0.7320	0.2492	0.3718
Constant Position Offset	5	DRL	0.9886	0.9630	0.9999	0.9811
		LSTM	0.7070	0.5203	0.2088	0.2981
		MLP	0.7084	0.5246	0.1786	0.2665
	10	DRL	0.9815	0.9415	0.9995	0.9696
		LSTM	0.7131	0.5565	0.1875	0.2805
		MLP	0.7168	0.5756	0.1912	0.2871
Random Speed	5	DRL	0.9900	0.9708	0.9967	0.9836
		LSTM	0.9522	0.9473	0.8876	0.9165
		MLP	0.9531	0.9539	0.8839	0.9176
	10	DRL	0.9882	0.9637	0.9983	0.9807
		LSTM	0.9509	0.9624	0.8674	0.9124
		MLP	0.9533	0.9642	0.8739	0.9168
Sybil	5	DRL	0.9999	0.9998	1.0000	0.9999
		LSTM	0.5512	0.9481	0.2947	0.4497
		MLP	0.6326	0.9098	0.4545	0.6062
	10	DRL	0.9999	0.9999	1.0000	0.9999
		LSTM	0.4994	0.8563	0.2331	0.3665
		MLP	0.6148	0.9477	0.4020	0.5645
Disruptive	5	DRL	0.9863	0.9561	1.0000	0.9778
		LSTM	0.7035	0.5265	0.0288	0.0547
		MLP	0.7028	0.5476	0.0041	0.0081
	10	DRL	0.9867	0.9578	1.0000	0.9785
		LSTM	0.7019	0.5909	0.0015	0.0031
		MLP	0.7018	0.4545	0.0003	0.0006
Data Replay	5	DRL	0.9868	0.9575	1.0000	0.9783
		LSTM	0.7079	0.6622	0.0383	0.0724
		MLP	0.7083	0.6603	0.0409	0.0771
	10	DRL	0.9865	0.9573	1.0000	0.9782
		LSTM	0.7089	0.6734	0.0397	0.0750
		MLP	0.7083	0.6378	0.0432	0.0809

robustness of the DRL policy is assessed under the most severe conditions.

1) Detection Performance under Label-flipping Attack:

Table I presents the performance results of our DRL-based approach and the benchmarks for the selected misbehavior types. Detection results indicate that the learned DRL policy effectively detects the label-flipping attack, achieving an F-score of approximately 0.97 or higher across all the analyzed misbehavior types, for both 5% and 10% of flipped labels. Attaining recall values of 1 or close to 1 for all the examined misbehavior types demonstrates the capability of the

DRL policy to correctly identify malicious samples, including those with flipped labels. In addition, high precision values underscore the capability of the DRL policy to effectively distinguish between genuine and malicious samples, including those affected by label-flipping, while tolerating FPs to an acceptable extent. The DRL agent incurs more penalties for FNs than FPs, resulting in slightly lower precision values compared to recall values. Furthermore, a slight decrease in detection performance can be noticed while maintaining superior values for all metrics, as the proportion of flipped labels increases from 5% to 10%. The effectiveness of the

Fig. 3: Average cumulative reward per training episode of the DRL agent.

label-flipping attack increases with the number of flipped labels. Notably, adversaries are unlikely to flip labels at high proportions to avoid detection and potential revocation from the vehicular communication system.

Fig. 3 illustrates the average cumulative reward per episode obtained by the DRL agent. It is apparent that the DRL agent consistently improves its decision-making to achieve higher detection performance while adapting to rapidly changing vehicular environments. Initially, during the agent-environment interactions, the accumulation of negative rewards indicates elevated false alarms as the DRL agent explores different actions. However, as the training advances, the agent gradually shifts towards exploitation by repeatedly taking similar actions. Consequently, this iterative process of detecting and learning with rewards enables the DRL-based approach to exhibit superior performance in the presence of various attacks.

On the contrary, Table I reveals that both MLP and LSTM classifiers are capable of detecting malicious samples moderately, including those affected by label-flipping, with the exception of the Random Speed misbehavior type where an F-score of close to 0.92 for both 5% and 10% of flipped labels (as shown in Fig. 4) is attained. By achieving significantly lower performance in terms of recall and F-score metrics across all the other misbehavior types, both MLP and LSTM models exhibit vulnerability to poisoning attacks such as label-flipping. As can be visually comprehended from Fig. 4, the inability of the two benchmark approaches to recognize intrinsic temporal and spatial interdependencies in the received BSMs is also revealed, especially when compared to the effectiveness of the DRL approach. In particular, the DRL scheme demonstrates the capability to enhance its detection performance through continuous exploration, adapting to rapidly changing vehicular environments.

2) *Robustness under Adversarial Perturbations:* Table II presents the detection performance outcomes of the DRL model, trained under policy induction attack, during test-time adversarial perturbations generated using various misbehavior

Fig. 4: Detection performance comparison based on F-score.

TABLE II: Detection performance under adversarial perturbations

Misbehavior Type	p	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-score
Constant Position	0.2	0.9158	0.7044	1.0000	0.8266
	1	0.5068	1.0000	0.5068	0.6727
Constant Position Offset	0.2	0.9152	0.7027	1.0000	0.8255
	1	0.5044	0.9998	0.5044	0.6706
Random Speed	0.2	0.9161	0.7054	1.0000	0.8273
	1	0.4951	1.0000	0.4951	0.6623
Sybil	0.2	0.9123	0.6956	1.0000	0.8205
	1	0.4942	0.9998	0.4942	0.6615
Disruptive	0.2	0.8584	0.6035	0.8552	0.7076
	1	0.5043	0.9999	0.5043	0.6705
Data Replay	0.2	0.9132	0.6957	1.0000	0.8206
	1	0.5020	1.0000	0.5020	0.6685

types. Results show that the DRL policy effectively detects adversarial perturbations with an F-score slightly exceeding 0.82, when the perturbations are injected in a non-continuous manner with $p=0.2$. Achieving significantly higher recall values further demonstrates the capability of the DRL policy to accurately identify perturbed inputs when generated with a lower frequency. Even under the most severe condition with $p=1$, the DRL policy remains moderately robust while detecting adversarial perturbations with an F-score of approximately 0.67. The recall values of approximately 0.5 exhibit that the ability of the DRL policy to effectively distinguish adversarial samples from genuine ones diminishes to a certain level under continuous adversarial perturbations. However, it is worth noting that in a dynamic vehicular environment, it is unlikely for an adversary to successfully generate perturbations for all observations of the target DRL agent.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed and evaluated a DRL-based adversarial defense approach for enhancing the security of vehicular communication systems. Performance results obtained from extensive evaluations showcase that our scheme effectively detects sophisticated poisoning attacks such as label-

flipping and policy induction. When compared with benchmark classifiers, our approach exhibits significantly superior performance in detecting label-flipping attacks. In particular, the DRL model achieves performance values close to or higher than 0.98 for accuracy, recall, and F-score metrics, emphasizing its effectiveness and superiority over its counterparts. Similarly, the model achieves significantly higher accuracy, recall, and F-score values, demonstrating its effectiveness in identifying adversarial manipulations. It is worth noting that even under the most severe conditions, the model maintains a moderate level of effectiveness, highlighting its robustness in the presence of adversarial manipulations. In future work, we plan to integrate adversarially robust learning techniques to enhance the DRL model's resilience against adversarial examples generated under physically realizable white-box attacks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially funded by the "Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital" and the European Union-NextGenerationEU in the frameworks of the "Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia" and the "Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia" under references TSI-063000-2021-39, TSI-063000-2021-40, TSI-063000-2021-41, and by the European Commission's Horizon Europe, Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking research and innovation program, under project VERGE (GA No. 101096034).

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